

CONCEPT OF SIRAVEDHA A LITERARY REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Acharya Sushruta is the father of ancient surgery. He has mentioned various method of *Raktamokshana* (Bloodletting). *Siravedha* is one of the important therapeutic venepuncture procedure described by *Acharya Sushruta* in his treatise *Sushruta Samhita*. *Siravedh* is an *Ardhchikitsa* in *Shalyatantra* while treating various types of disease. It is highly effective in expelling vitiated *Dosha*, thereby restoring the *Dosha Dhatu Samyata* (balancing the elements of the human body). *Siravedh* is single therapeutic procedure in order to treat a diseased condition. In *Sushruta Samhita* *Siravedh* as a prime modality in the management of various disorders. In eighth chapter of *Sushruta Sharirsthana* the detail description of *Siravedh* is given. It include appropriate time, method of venesection, indication and contra-indication of *Siravedha*. The procedure is

to be helpful in *Kushtha* (skin disorder), *Gridhrasi* (Sciatica), *Vatrakta* (gout), hypertention related condition, certain vascular condition etc. The present study focus on literary review of *Siravedha* and probable mode action of procedure.

KEYWORD: *Siravedha*, bloodletting, *Kushtha*, *Gridhrasi*, *Vatrakta*.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda, the ancient indian system of medicine, emphasizes both preventive and curative measures for maintaining health and treating diseases. The art of healing is one of the intellectual properties of the human beings originated out of constraint, need of self-protection and the urge to help. *Ayurveda* addresses that let the noxious blood be let out it will cure the diseases. The *Raktmokshan* means to let out the blood. The word *Siravedha*

contain two word *Sira* means the anatomical structure through which slow flowing of blood occur and *Vedhana* means to puncture.

Acharya Sushruta stated that *Siravedha* is *Ardhachikitsa* in *Shalyatantra* due to its wide applicability in various types of disorder. It is one of the five *Panchakarma* procedure for detoxification of the body. It is one of the *Shodhan* procedure where the vitiated *Dosh* expelled from the body by creating artificial route by removing considerable amount of blood in well controlled manner. The procedure is to be helpful in *Kushtha* (skin disorder), *Gridhrasi* (Sciatica), *Vatrakta* (gout), hypertension related condition, certain vascular condition.^[6] Classical text highlight the importance of proper vein selection, puncturing a selected *Sira* (vein), seasonal considerations, preoperative and postoperative protocol to ensure safety and efficacy.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVE

To explain and explore the concept of *Siravedha*.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Bruhatrayee along with their commentaries by different authors. Different references from modern sciences to correlate.

DISCUSSION

Raktmokshana broadly classified into two types.^[9]

1. *Shatrakruta*- Process Perform with the help of sharp instrument.

- *Jalauka*
- *Alabu*
- *Shrung*

2. *Ashatrakruta*- Process Perform without use of sharp instrument.

- *Prachhan*
- *Siravedha*

So the *Siravedha* is one of the type of *Shatrakrut Raktmokshana*.

Indication of *Siravedha*^[7]

- *Vidradhi* (Abscess)
- *Gridhrasi* (Sciatica)

- *Updansh* (Gonorrhoea)
- *Arbud* (Tumour)
- *Kushtha* (Skin disease)
- *Sleepada* (Filariasis)
- *Ekdeshaj shoth* (Edema)
- *Vatarakta* (Gout)
- *Stanroga* (Disease of breast)

Contraindication in *Siravedha*^[1]

- *Udara* (Ascites)
- *Pandu* (Anaemia)
- *Arsha* (Haemorrhoid)
- *Garbhini* (Pregnant women)
- *Ssarvangshoph* (Anasarca)
- *Ksheena* (malnourished)

Appropriate time for *Siravedha*^[3]

- *Hemanta rutu* (Winter season) - *Madhyahana* (Afternoon time)
- *Grishma rutu* (Summer season) – Environment is cool (Morning hour)
- *Varsha rutu* (Rainy season) – when sky is clear

Amount of blood withdraw^[5]

- 1 *Prastha* – Around 768 ml of blood but practically it is not possible. Assess the patient *Bala* (Built) and *Vyadhibala* (chronicity of disease) then it is decided by the *Vaidya*.

Procedure of *Siravedha*^[2]

1. Pre-operative procedure

- The patient should be fed with *Yavagu* (liquid food diet)
- *Snehan* (Oleation therapy) and *Swedan* (fomentation therapy)
- Patient is made to seat in comfortable position facing the east direction. The site of punctured should be properly clean.
- The cloth should be tied 1 finger breadth above the site to be punctured.

2. Operative procedure
 - Vein is punctured with sharp instrument.
 - First vitiated blood flows which is slightly dark in color.
3. Post-operative procedure
 - Measure the amount of blood withdraw.
 - Make Patient comfortable give some rest to him.

***Samyak Suvidha Sira Lakshana*^[4] (Symptoms of adequate blood flow)**

- *Laghava* (Feeling lightness in the body)
- *Vedanashanti* (Relief from pain)
- *Manaprasada* (Feeling of wellness in the mind)
- After proper *Siravedha* blood clots after sometime.

***Atipravruta Lakshana*^[8] (Symptoms of excessive blood flow)**

- *Timira* (Blackouts in the front of eyes)
- *Aandhya* (Blindness)
- *Akshepaka* (Seizures)
- *Pakshaghat* (Paralysis)
- *Daha* (Burning sensation)
- *Trishna* (Thirst)
- *Marama* (Death)

Benefits of *Siravedha*

- It help to eliminate the vitiated *Dosh* from body. It give relief from the symptoms of various disorder.
- It is performed in OPD.
- It is safe and cost effective to patient.

Precaution in *Siravedha*

- Check the vitals of the body while performing procedure.
- It is carried out under strict aseptic condition to prevent further complication.

Acharya *Sushruta* stated that *Siravedha* is *Ardhachikitsa* in *Shalyatantra*. *Siravedha* can be correlate with venipuncture but it is differ in few aspect. It is more therapeutic procedure

rather than a diagnostic procedure. So we can manage some surgical disorder with the help of *Siravedha* in OPD.

CONCLUSION

Sira is an anatomical structure through which substances flow. In general the term *Sira* stand for blood vessel veins. *Sira* are *Sarvavaha* in nature there is no *Sira* in the body which carries either the *Vayu*, *Pitta* and *Kapha*. Some *Sira* are contraindicated for venesection called *Avedhya Sira*. *Siravedha* is a scientifically relevant *Ayurvedic* parasurgical procedure that offer significant therapeutic benefits in chronic, refractory and blood related disorder. The probable mechanism may involve the improved blood circulation, detoxification and modulation of immune responses. This literary review suggest that *Siravedha* effectively eliminates vitiated *Dosh* and provide relief in condition associated with *Rakta Dushti* and obstructed microcirculation. Furthermore evidence based clinical studies in *Siravedha* validate its efficacy.

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